

Essential Oils of Travancore. Part VII.
From the Rhizome of Ginger, *Zingiber officinale*.

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Ginger is cultivated, more or less, all over the hilly tracts in Travancore, but its cultivation on a large scale is confined to Ettumanur and Meenachil Taluks and to parts of Kottayam and Chanancherry Taluks. The cultivation commences in the middle of May and the crop is harvested in the middle of December. The green rhizomes contain 70-80 per cent. of water and are dried for export. For this purpose the upper coating is scraped and the scraped ginger is either dried in the sun without further treatment or limed and dried. The latter operation bleaches the root more effectively. The ginger scrapings are generally thrown into a pond along with cattle manure and sweepings, and merely serve to enrich the liquid manure which is used for the next crop. A large quantity of ginger is exported from Travancore but the essential oil obtainable from the roots by distillation with steam, a well-known commercial product, is not manufactured locally. Since there is no specific mention in the literature about the Travancore oil having been investigated, the work described below was undertaken with a view to study the properties and the composition of this oil. While this paper was in manuscript, Sanjiva Rao, Sudborough and Watson (*J. Indian Inst. of Sci.*, 1925, Part X, Vol. VIIIA, 151) published the constants of an oil obtained by them at Bangalore from waste ginger which consists of *rejected ginger* and scrapings. Their results are compared in this paper.

It has been found that the constants of the oil from the local ginger agree very closely with those of the oil obtained from the Jamaica or African rhizomes (Table I). The chief constituent of the oil is zingiberene (70 per cent.), a sesquiterpene hydrocarbon, to the presence of which the high laevo-rotation of the oil is due. On heating or, on prolonged contact with air, this compound was found to undergo very great change indicated most prominently by the

change of the laevo-rotation ($[\alpha]_D^{15}$ about -65°) to dextro-rotation ($[\alpha]_D^{15}$ about $+5^\circ$).

The oil undergoes the same change but less rapidly. This change has been studied for the oil and the fraction rich in zingiberene.

The optical rotation, determined in this laboratory, for the oil from dry ginger was considerably higher than the maximum rotation recorded by other investigators. As the constants were determined within a few hours of the distillation of the oil and as the optical rotation diminished on keeping, this apparent discrepancy does not prejudice the inclusion of this oil among normal trade oils. The constants of the oil obtained by Rao, Sudborough and Watson (*loc. cit.*) lie, as expected, between those of the oil from ginger alone and the oil from the scrapings (Table I). The higher proportion of alcohols found in the Bangalore oil (ester value after acetylation 49.8) is presumably contributed by the scrapings in the waste ginger (ester value after acetylation 103, author).

A small quantity of oil was obtained from fresh ginger supplied by the Agricultural Farm, near Trivandrum. The constants of the oil show that though it differs from the oils obtained from different samples of dry ginger, this difference is not sufficiently pronounced to exclude this oil from the normal oils of trade. The ginger scrapings, at present utilised only as manure, were found to yield, when distilled in the usual manner, an oil which differs greatly from the oil from the rhizomes. The solubility of the oil and its higher ester value indicate that it is much richer in oxygenated products, and as these are prized in perfumery, it would be of interest to obtain a quantity of the oil so that a more elaborate examination may be made. This work is projected.

Ginger leaves also possess a faint aroma of ginger but no oil could be obtained by distillation with steam.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Two samples of ginger, one fresh and the other one year old, were crushed and distilled with steam (60 lbs. pressure) in a small still of about 10 gallons capacity. The scrapings were distilled separately and without previous treatment.* The oils did not

* It may be mentioned that as the scrapings had to be brought over a long distance a certain amount of rot had set in which may have slightly effected the oil from the scrapings.

possess the pungent taste of ginger which is due to the presence of a ketone, zingerone which is not volatile in steam (*cf.* Nomura, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 111, 769; Lapworth, Pearson and Royle, *ibid.*, p. 777).

TABLE I.

	Trade (i).	Bangalore.	Author.			
			Fresh dry.	One year dry.	Green.	Scrapings.
Yield per cent.	.. 2 to 3	... 3.54	2.0	1.8	0.8	0.9
Colour Pale yellow to dark yellow	Golden	Light-yellow	Brownish yellow	Yellow	Brown
D_{D}^{27} 0.8740 to 0.8860	(ii) 0.8822	0.8690	0.8733	0.8800	0.8816
$[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -25° to -50°	(ii) -39°2	-51°0	-52°2	-26°1	-9°85'
n_D^{26} 1.4885 to 1.4950	(ii) 1.4898	1.4891	1.4890	1.4878	1.4862
Acid value	... 0 to 2	... 2.1	1.0	0.8	...	1.0
Ester value	... 1 to 15	... 7.7	7.4	6.0	...	10.0
Ester value after acetylation.	30 to 45	... 49.8	30.5	35.9	...	103.0
Solubility. Vols. Insol of 90 per cent. alcohol.	Insol.	Insol	Insol	10 vols.

(i) Parry, "The Chemistry of Essential Oils and Artificial Perfumes," Fourth Edition, Vol. I. p. 99.

(ii) D_{D}^{15} , $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, n_D^{25}

As only small quantities of the oils from green ginger and ginger scrapings were available, the following work was carried out with the oil obtained from dry ginger only.

A small quantity of the oil (50 c.c.) was distilled from the essential oil flask, Schimmel pattern (3 bulbs), under atmospheric pressure

and the following fractions obtained. The yields are compared with those obtained by Thresh and quoted by Parry (*loc. cit.* p. 99) and by Rao, Sudborough and Watson.

TABLE II.

Boiling point.	Author.	Yield per cent.			$[\alpha]_D^{30}$ (Author).
		Thresh.	Bangalore p=685 mm.		
Below 150°	2.4	5.0	1.4	+53°	
150°–200°	9.4	10.0	5.0	+26°	
200°–240°	5.4	8.0	12.3	+15°	
240°–265°	70.2	60.0	40.0	+9°	
265°–300°	3.2	7.0	20.8		
Residue (difference)	9.4	10.0	11.5		

It would appear from the rotations of the various fractions recorded above that the oil undergoes change at the high temperatures required for the above distillation under ordinary pressure. Separate portions of the oil were heated for an hour at different temperatures with a view to find out the temperature at which the above changes become markedly noticeable.

TABLE III.

$[\alpha]_D^{30}$	Temperature of heating.						
	Not heated	100°	125°	175°	190°	240°	
						1 hour	2 hours
	-52°24	-49°6	-46°0	-45°8	-28°35	+4°8	+5°0

This shows that fractionation under reduced pressure would help to separate the different fractions unaltered, for the oil undergoes but little change below 175°. The oil was fractionated into four fractions (Table IV). The dextrorotation of the first fraction is due to *d*-camphene identified by converting to *iso*-borneol. The major fraction (3), was distilled repeatedly over sodium and, finally an oil with the constants given below obtained (Table V). Values obtained for zingiberene by von Soden and Rojahn are also given.

TABLE IV.

No.	B. pt./3mm.	Yield per cent.	Colour	30° D	30° [α] D	30° n D
1	50° to 90°	10.0	Colourless	0.8638	+24.41	1.4600
2	90° to 116°	12.5	„	0.8708	-37.25	1.4860
3	119° to 123°	70.0	„	0.8638	-64.00	1.4870
4	Above 123°	6.5	Pale yellow			
5	Residue	1.0				

TABLE V.

	Author	von Soden and Rojahn
30° [α] D	-64.0	—
30° [α] D	-73.7	-73.0
30° n D	1.4916	1.49399 at 15°
Specific gravity	0.8690 at 30°	0.8730 at 20°

The nitrosite was obtained by treating freshly distilled zingiberene in petrol solution with a solution of sodium nitrite and glacial acetic acid. A crop of silky fine needles was obtained which melted at 92°-94°. This compound is stated to be unstable by Schreiner and Kremers, m. p. 98°. The crystals obtained above appeared to be quite stable in outward appearance but the melting point was found to vary from time to time, increasing steadily till, after six months, it reached a maximum of 113°. A sample of zingiberene which had been kept in a loose stoppered container for three months did not give a nitrosite. It was found to have altered greatly in constants (Rotation +2.3, density 0.9345, index of refraction 1.502). This was taken to be due to the exposure to air and the following work was done to study the effect of heating and exposure to air on the compound.

Effect of Heating.—A quantity of zingiberene was heated on a sand-bath to gentle boiling for 45 minutes. The resulting oil was

dextrorotatory and viscous. It was distilled under reduced pressure and the major fraction thus obtained refractionated carefully (Tables VI and VII). Semmler and Becker who studied zingiberene in detail tried the effect of heat on a mixture of zingiberene and isoprene. They obtained a mixture which was found to contain limonene, a bicyclic sesquiterpene which they named *meta*-zingiberene and a diterpene. As has been stated above, a complex change takes place when zingiberene is heated alone. That this is not due to the conversion of zingiberene to *isozingiberene* is borne out by the constants of the two fractions obtained by refractionating fraction 2. (Table VI.) Apparently zingiberene is altered to another dextrorotatory monocyclic sesquiterpene and not the dicyclic *isozingiberene* whose constants would readily differentiate it from the two fractions A and B below (Table VII).

TABLE VI.

No.	B. p. /5mm.	Yield per cent.	30°	27°	30°
			D 4°	n 4°	[α] D
1.	Below 110°	4			
2.	110°–130°	52	0.8902	1.496	+6°.5
3.	Above 130°	12			
4.	Residue	32			

TABLE VII.

	A	B	<i>isozingiberene</i> .
B. pt.	... up to 265°	265°–270°	118°/7 mm.
n_D^{30}	... 1.492	1.491	1.5062
n_D^{27}	.. 0.8788	0.8835	0.9118
n_D^{40}	.. 0.8788	0.8835	0.9118
[α] _D ³⁰	... +6°.9	+7°.8	-51.36

Effect of Exposure of Zingiberene to Air.—The following experiments were undertaken with a view to study the changes brought about in zingiberene on exposure to air. Purified zingiberene was divided into three equal portions. One was sealed in a tube (a), another kept in a tube of the same size plugged with cotton wool (b), and the third in a conical flask similarly plugged (c). The constants of these were determined from time to time. As the refractive index could be determined without much loss of material, the changes were followed with the help of the refractometer, the rotations being determined occasionally. A comparison of the graphs of these show that air plays an important part

n the change, the small change undergone by the specimen in the tube (a) being attributable to the residual air in it at the time of the sealing. Another experiment confirmed this. The specimen which had been kept in the sealed tube for 19 days without much change was divided into two portions. Air was bubbled through one during eight hours and the other was left plugged for the same period. As expected, the latter underwent but little change whilst the former was found to have altered greatly (rotation +6.35°, index of refraction 1.5088.) Similar experiments were tried with ginger oil which was found to undergo similar changes, though more slowly than the high percentage of zingiberene would lead one to expect. It is probable that the change is inhibited by the other components of the oil (Tables VIII, IX and X also graphs).

OPTICAL ROTATION CURVES.

REFRACTIVE INDICES CURVES

TABLE VIII.

Effect of Exposure of Zingiberene to Air.

		Number of days.							
		Sample	0	6	8	17	19	20	23
n	D	(a)	1'4916	1'4918
		(b)	1'4916	1'4930	1'4934	1'4948	1'4954	1'4968	1'4963
		(c)	1'4916	1'4995	1'5013	1'5058	...	1'5067	1'5073
[a]	D	(a)	-64'0°	-63'15°
		(b)	-64°'0	-60°'6	-33'2°	...
		(c)	-64°'0	-15°'0	+12'5°	+12'5°
D	4°	(a)	0'8693
		(ā)	0'8693	0'8700
		(b)	0'8693	0'8860	...	0'8910
		(c)	0'8693	0'9154

TABLE IX.

Effect of Exposure of Ginger Oil to Air.

		Number of days.						
		Sample	0	18	24	35	40	43
[a]	D	Sealed	-54'0°	-54'0°
		Plugged	-54'0	-53°'75	-50'2°
n	D	Sealed	1'4890	1'4905
		Plugged	1'4890	1'4905	1'4912	1'4921	1'4922	1'4923

TABLE X.

Exposure of Ginger Oil to Air (air bubbled through).

		Time-hours.					
		Original	4	8	12	16	
n	D		1'4920	1'4925	1'4931	1'4938	1'4945
		[a]	-52'0	-49°'6

Summary.

1. The essential oil obtained from dry ginger produced in Travancore is normal in character and can be obtained in a yield of 2 per cent. The yield diminished with the age of ginger.

2. Green ginger and ginger scrapings yield an essential oil differing in some respects from the oil from the dry roots.

3. The leaves yield no oil.

4. Ginger oil undergoes change on heating and on prolonged exposure to air. The oil cannot be distilled under ordinary pressure and it should be kept in well-stoppered bottles.

5. Zingiberene changes more readily on heating or on contact with air. At present there is no evidence to show that the changes are identical.

5. On heating at its boiling point, zingiberene yields a monocyclic dextrorotatory sesquiterpene and an undistillable semi-solid residue.

Further work is projected. The thanks of the author are due to the Director of Industries, Travancore, for supplying the materials for distillations and to Mr. P. N. Vridhachalam, B.A., who supervised them.

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